

Universidade de Brasília

Instituto de Psicologia

Departamento de Processos Psicológicos Básicos

Programa de Pós-Graduação em Ciências do Comportamento

Formalizing the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI): A Behavioral Engineering Framework for the Monitoring of Continuous Aversive Stimulation in Digital Forensic Examiners

Frederico Santos Veloso

Dr. Carlos Eduardo Palhares Machado

Prof.^a Dr.^a Adriana Manso Melchiades

University of Brasília, Graduate Program in Behavioral Sciences

Abstract

Traditional models of occupational health in cybercrime forensics frequently rest on internalist constructs (e.g., secondary trauma) that are difficult to measure continuously and of limited use for systems engineering. This work proposes the formalization of the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI), a continuous environmental variable that synthesizes severity, duration, and rate of contact, and presents the framework of the SUPREME V4 system.

Grounded in Behavior Analysis, the model conceives of exposure load as a variable with a motivational function analogous to an Establishing Operation (EO), capable of modulating the value of negative reinforcement and influencing the probability of escape and avoidance responses, observable through behavioral telemetry (e.g., latency and response rate).

The architecture integrates three analytic axes: environmental load (OEI), operant telemetry (logs), and verbal behavior (psychometrics), enabling the identification of patterns

of functional divergence between behavioral measures and self-report at pre-symptomatic levels.

The present article establishes the ontological, mathematical, and architectural foundations of the model, proposing an agnostic protocol for continuous measurement in high aversive-load contexts. Empirical calibration of the parameters is under way in a naturalistic pilot study.

Keywords: Occupational Exposure Index; Behavior Analysis; Establishing Operation; negative reinforcement; avoidance; behavioral telemetry; digital forensics; CSAM exposure; occupational health; continuous measurement; behavioral engineering; longitudinal data

1. Introduction

The description of the psychological effects associated with high aversive-load occupational contexts, such as the forensic examination of child sexual abuse material (CSAM), has been conducted primarily from models centered on internalist constructs, especially secondary trauma. These models were important for characterizing the problem and organizing its most frequent clinical outcomes, such as post-traumatic stress, anxiety, depression, and occupational exhaustion. Even so, they present important limitations when the goal is no longer merely to describe suffering already in place and instead involves continuous monitoring of occupational exposure or the development of systems able to operate on observable environmental variables. In general, these approaches rely on retrospective reports and subjective indicators, which hinders a more precise identification of the relations between characteristics of the work environment and gradual changes in the behavioral repertoire of examiners.

The available empirical literature suggests the relevance of this shift in perspective. In a study with roughly 500 North American professionals involved in CSAM analysis, Mitchell et al. observed that the severity of the analyzed material was the only factor independently associated with an increase in post-traumatic stress symptoms. Among British investigators, Gullon-Scott and Johnson found a prevalence of approximately 30% of secondary traumatic

stress at severe levels, a result the authors related to institutional contexts in which the expression of suffering tends to be socially inhibited. More recently, the Self-Assessment Tool developed by Mitchell et al. represented an important advance by organizing subjective indicators of occupational risk. Even so, the instrument remains restricted to self-report and to the isolated analysis of specific variables.

As far as the present literature review allowed us to verify, there are no published models that treat occupational exposure to CSAM as a continuous variable inferred from behavioral telemetry obtained in the natural work environment. It is precisely this gap that the present study seeks to investigate.

It is at this point that the present work differs. Rather than starting from inferred internal states, the analysis is organized around the functional relations between environment and behavior. In this formulation, occupational exposure ceases to be treated merely as a descriptive marker of psychological suffering and comes to be understood as a continuous environmental variable, capable of altering the probability and the temporal organization of escape and avoidance responses and other patterns of behavioral deterioration under prolonged aversive contingencies.

To this end, the work introduces SUPREME V4 (System for Unified Psychometric and Remote Extraction of Multimodal Exposure), a continuous measurement system developed to operationalize the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI). The OEI is defined as a continuous environmental variable that integrates severity, duration, and rate of contact with the analyzed material. As this intensity increases, the reinforcing value of the relief produced by interrupting, reducing, or avoiding contact with aversive stimuli also changes, modifying the probability of escape and avoidance responses. These effects are estimated through behavioral markers extracted by telemetry over the operational routine of the examiners.

In the proposed model, the OEI corresponds to the theoretical environmental construct used to describe the density of aversive stimulation present in the work environment. Its quantitative operationalization occurs through the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI), defined as the computational representation of this variable from observable parameters collected during forensic activity.

1.1 The Engineering Ontology of SUPREME V4

SUPREME V4 is grounded in the tradition of Behavior Analysis, particularly in the conception of behavior as a function of environmental contingencies, as established by Skinner (1938, 1953). In this tradition, the analytic focus falls on the functional relations between the organism and its environment, taking observable interactions between the two as the unit of analysis.

Understanding behavior in this tradition requires a systematic description of how environmental variables take part in its control, including antecedents and consequences organized into contingencies. In the context of digital forensics, this implies treating forensic platforms as environmental arrangements that structure and modulate the examiner's behavior throughout the analysis.

Systems such as Griffeye Analyze, Cellebrite UFED, and IPED configure operational contexts in which responses are evoked, maintained, and organized by specific contingencies. This perspective makes it possible to build measurable and operational models, in which environmental events and response patterns are defined, recorded, and analyzed with precision, situating SUPREME V4 as a system that treats the digital environment as an object of continuous measurement through indicators derived from permanent products.

Building on this characterization of the platforms, SUPREME V4 establishes a second level of analysis directed at the continuous measurement of behavior. At this level, the examiner's interactions are treated as permanent products of behavior, that is, observable records that persist after the response has occurred (Skinner, 1953), becoming amenable to systematic capture through digital logs. From these records, operant metrics such as latency, pauses, avoidance patterns, and variations in response rate are derived, composing an empirical base of high temporal resolution and reducing dependence on self-reports.

It is on this base that the level of functional analysis is built. The extracted metrics are integrated into a quantitative system that formalizes properties of the digital environment as functional variables. The OEI synthesizes severity, duration, and rate of contact into a continuous index. This formalization makes it possible to model how variations in the

environment modulate the value of consequences and the probability of response over time, making it possible to identify risk trajectories and critical points for data-based intervention.

The system adopts as its unit of analysis observable properties of behavior, such as rate, latency, and temporal distribution of responses, as described by B. F. Skinner and C. B. Ferster (1957), extracted from operational records treated as permanent products under specific contingencies. Aversiveness is defined functionally as a relation between organism and environment and is operationalized through measurable dimensions of the exposure flow.

1.2 The OEI as an Aversive Establishing Operation

SUPREME V4 records observable behavioral events in the interaction with the digital environment, treated as permanent products of behavior and organized into temporal sequences that allow the extraction of observable properties, through logs. These records constitute a continuous measure of the functional relation between the organism and the environmental contingencies operationalized in the platform, enabling the quantitative modeling of occupational exposure.

The Occupational Exposure Intensity does not refer to the physical magnitude of the stimulus itself, but to its function as an environmental variable that alters the value of consequences and the probability of responses. Intensity is operationally defined as the capacity of the stimulus arrangement to modulate negative reinforcement relations over time, consistent with the concept of establishing operation.

The central hypothesis states that the OEI acts in a manner analogous to a conditioned establishing operation, momentarily altering the effectiveness of relief as a negative reinforcer. Under this condition, escape and avoidance responses become more probable, operationalized through micro-variations in operant telemetry: increased latency, a rise in the frequency of interruptions, and changes in re-engagement time, estimated by behavioral markers recorded by telemetry.

These variations indicate a transition in the control of behavior, in which the response ceases to be predominantly under the control of the task stimuli and comes to be modulated by

the motivating operation, consistent with the effects of aversive control described by Murray Sidman.

Treated as an environmental motivational parameter, the OEI makes it possible to measure changes in the relative effectiveness of competing reinforcers over the course of exposure. Rather than representing the cost of the response, the OEI expresses the modulation of the functional value of relief, allowing the identification of changes in the organism's sensitivity to negative reinforcement contingencies. This approach makes it possible to detect transformations in the repertoire at levels prior to the consolidation of clinical indicators, shifting the focus of measurement from internal states to the analysis of the dynamics of control that organize behavior over time.

A complementary formulation specifies the historical dimension of this process: the OEI may operate as a reflexive conditioned establishing operation, in Jack Michael's terms, in which the accumulation of exposure comes to signal the probability of deterioration of environmental conditions. In this configuration, the reinforcing value of relief depends not only on the aversive stimulation present, but on the predictive function acquired over the recent history of interaction, such that task interruption comes to be evoked under the control of an anticipatory gradient, and not merely a reactive one. This phenomenon is analogous to what contemporary cognitive psychology describes as attentional bias toward threatening stimuli: the recent history of exposure pre-activates avoidance patterns before the current stimulus reaches a sufficient threshold (Bar-Haim et al., 2007; MacLeod et al., 2002).

This distinction has relevant functional implications: whereas a simple establishing operation predicts avoidance under the control of the present stimulus, the reflexive conditioned form implies anticipatory avoidance, offering a functional interpretation for patterns in which behavioral reorganizations emerge early over the course of accumulated exposure.

1.3 Behavioral Engineering Audit: Dynamics of Concurrent Contingencies in SUPREME V4

The functional analysis of the digital forensics context indicates that the examiner's behavior occurs under an ecology of concurrent contingencies, organized at different levels of control. At the macro level, forensic activity is embedded in fixed-interval schedules, intermittent reinforcement, and institutional contingencies of high reinforcing value, including occupational stability, remuneration, and professional status. This arrangement configures a functionally closed contingency, in which total escape responses, such as leave of absence or abandonment of the role, are associated with high punitive costs, restricting their probability of occurrence (Ferster & Skinner, 1957; Sidman, 1989).

Under this configuration, the examiner's behavior remains under the control of contingencies that maintain engagement in the task, even in the face of intense and repeated aversive stimulation. This is an applied case of behavior under coercive control, in which the absence of functional escape alternatives heightens the organism's dependence on local relief strategies (Sidman, 1989).

It is at this point that SUPREME V4 carries out its central analytic function: the micro-functional analysis of behavior. While the macro arrangement keeps the examiner in the task, the OEI, conceived as a variable that acts in a manner analogous to a conditioned establishing operation, continuously modulates the value of the consequences available in the environment. As described by Michael (1993), establishing operations simultaneously produce value-altering effects, by increasing the effectiveness of a reinforcer, and evocative effects, by increasing the probability of responses that have historically produced that reinforcer.

In digital forensics, the progressive increase in the OEI raises the reinforcing value of immediate relief, that is, of interrupting or reducing contact with aversive stimuli. In parallel, it evokes escape and avoidance responses in the examiner's operant repertoire, even in the absence of changes in the institutional contingencies that sustain their permanence in the role.

In terms of behavioral engineering, this phenomenon corresponds to a transition in the stimulus control of operant behavior. Initially, the examiner's response is under discriminative control of the relevant stimulus (S^D), that is, the informational properties of the evidence that guide the technical analysis. As the OEI rises, a progressive transfer of this control to the

aversive establishing operation is observed, such that the response comes to be emitted under the control of the need to reduce contact with the stimulus.

This transition implies a functional reorganization of the response topography: from a pattern of discriminative observation oriented toward analysis, to an avoidance pattern that accelerates over time. As a consequence, the quality of the forensic product tends to be affected, not by a limitation in technical competence, but by a change in the contingencies that control the emission of behavior (Rachlin, 1994; Sidman, 1989).

1.3.1 Functional Divergence between Verbal Behavior and Operant Behavior

The proposed model differentiates verbal behavior and operant behavior on the basis of their function and the contingencies that control them, with emphasis on the possible divergence between these response classes. Psychometric measures are treated as verbal behavior under the control of social contingencies. By contrast, the behavioral telemetry derived from operational logs constitutes a direct record of operant behavior under immediate environmental control, as described by B. F. Skinner.

This distinction makes it possible to identify patterns of functional dissociation. In certain situations, the examiner reports emotional stability, inferred from the absence of elevation on psychometric scales, while telemetry data indicate increased latency, fragmentation of engagement, and the recurrent occurrence of micro-pauses. A decoupling between response systems is thus configured.

This pattern is interpreted as the result of differential control by contingencies: verbal behavior remains under the control of social reinforcers that favor the maintenance of an image of stability, while operant behavior is already under the control of the aversive establishing operation. Such dissociation constitutes functional evidence that changes in the behavioral repertoire may temporally precede the emergence of psychometric indicators of suffering, a pattern corroborated by ecological momentary assessment (EMA) evidence showing that direct behavioral indicators detect functional deterioration before self-report captures it (Kimhy et al.,

2020; Trull & Ebner-Priemer, 2020), and it is the pattern of greatest diagnostic value in the system.

1.3.2 Measurement of the Establishing Operation and Analytic Implications

The conceptualization of the OEI as an establishing operation defines specific criteria for its measurement. As a functional variable, its relevance lies in its capacity to predict systematic changes in behavior, beyond the mere quantification of exposure.

The mathematical formalization of the OEI makes it possible to model its relation to behavior through nonlinear functions, in which equivalent increments in exposure produce disproportionate variations in the probability of escape and avoidance responses. Applying a logistic transformation to the index makes this relation explicit across the exposure continuum and allows the identification of regions of greater sensitivity, in which small variations in the OEI produce abrupt changes in response probability, characterizing inflection points between regimes of behavioral control.

These points correspond to thresholds at which the evocative and value-altering effects of the establishing operation become sufficiently intense to reorganize the operant repertoire. Empirically, such transitions can be inferred from the relation between an increase in the OEI, changes in telemetry indicators (e.g., latency, interruptions), and a subsequent elevation in psychometric measures.

Although the empirical validation of these thresholds is an objective of subsequent studies, the structure of the model already makes it possible to operationalize, in a naturalistic context, the continuous measurement of motivational processes traditionally described only in experimental settings. SUPREME V4 quantifies occupational exposure and records, in real time, the functional dynamics by which the value of relief rises and the operant repertoire reorganizes under aversive control.

1.4 High Temporal Resolution Telemetry

The architecture of SUPREME V4 rests on two complementary requirements of behavior analysis. The first is the molar definition of behavior, as proposed by Howard Rachlin (1994, 2000), in which the object of analysis is patterns extended in time, and not isolated discrete responses. The second is the need for continuous measurement of these patterns, as established by Ogden Lindsley (1991), which makes it possible to observe behavior in its real temporal dimension.

Behavior is treated as a flow and measurement as the continuous recording of that flow. The system's telemetry operates precisely at this point of intersection: by recording interactions at high temporal resolution, it allows behavioral trajectories to be reconstructed as patterns organized over time, making variations in pace, persistence, interruption, and acceleration under different environmental conditions analyzable.

The integration between this temporal resolution and metadata on content severity, derived from standardized international classification systems such as the COPINE scale, makes it possible to articulate two frequently dissociated dimensions: the temporal structure of behavior and the functional load of the environment. Incorporated into this context, this classification comes to operate as a criterion for metrifying the intensity of the aversiveness associated with the analyzed material. SUPREME V4 makes it possible to examine, in a naturalistic context, how variations in exposure intensity modulate the behavioral flow over time.

1.5 Objective

The present article aims to formalize the theoretical and mathematical foundations of the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI) and to describe the architecture of the SUPREME V4 system as an instrument of behavioral measurement. In addition, it seeks to formalize the operational definition of the OEI as a continuous environmental variable and its application in longitudinal monitoring contexts, describing a technically structured proposal for the measurement of contingencies in digital environments.

2. Formalization of the Mathematical Parameters of the OEI

The Occupational Exposure Index (OEI) is defined as a composite continuous variable intended to quantify the functional magnitude of aversive stimulation within a defined time window. Its construction involves the definition of observable variables, temporal aggregation, intraindividual standardization, nonlinear transformation, and incorporation of temporal dependence.

2.1 Fundamental Exposure Variables

The OEI derives from four observable dimensions of the organism-environment interaction.

Exposure Time (T)

Total duration of contact with the stimulus environment within a defined time window.

Event Frequency (E)

Number of recorded behavioral interactions, including viewings and classifications.

Weighted Exposure Volume (V)

Functional magnitude of aversive stimulation, defined as:

$$W_{evento} = s_k \cdot m_k$$

where:

- s_k denotes the severity of the event k
- m_k denotes the weight of the media type

The media multipliers are defined as operational constants:

- image = 1.0
- video = 1.5
- preview = 0.5

Severity is binarized:

- Alpha class = 1.0
- Beta class = 5.0

Given the asymmetry of the distribution, the following is applied:

Implementation note: in aggregation by biweekly window, V must be computed as a sum weighted by session time. That is, $V = \sum (W_{\text{event}} \times \text{dur}_{\text{min}})$, where dur_{min} is the session duration in minutes. This weighting ensures that two examiners with the same number of events and the same severity, but with distinct exposure durations, produce proportionally different values of V , preserving functional coherence with the weight α assigned to duration in the linear combination. The logarithmic transformation $V_{\text{log}} = \log(1 + V)$ is applied over this already weighted volume.

$$V_{\log} = \log(1 + V)$$

Temporal Density (D)

Rate of events per unit of time:

$$D = \frac{E}{T}$$

2.2 Intraindividual Standardization

Each variable is transformed into a standardized score relative to the individual baseline:

$$z_X = \frac{X - \mu_X}{\sigma_X}$$

where

μ_X and σ_X are the individual's mean and standard deviation. For volume, V_{log} is used.

This transformation expresses each dimension as a deviation relative to the organism's own historical standard.

2.3 Linear Combination of Environmental Load

The composite environmental load is defined by:

$$IEO_{linear} = \alpha z_T + \beta z_E + \gamma z_V$$

with:

- $\alpha > \beta > \gamma$
- $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$

Initial values:

- $\alpha = 0.5, \beta = 0.3, \gamma = 0.2$

The weights reflect the differential function of the variables:

- continuous duration of exposure
- repetition of contact
- qualitative magnitude

The values are provisional and will be adjusted by longitudinal modeling, based on the relation between the OEI and observable changes in telemetry and psychometric measures.

The variable z_D (temporal density) does not enter the linear combination for a structural reason: $D = E / T$, so that z_D is algebraically dependent on z_E and z_T . Including it in the linear combination would introduce partial multicollinearity, artificially inflating the weight of the frequency and duration dimensions and compromising the interpretability of the coefficients α , β , and γ . By being added after logistic saturation as an independent additive term, density captures the effect of instantaneous temporal pressure without distorting the structure of the linear combination of the principal components.

2.4 Logistic Saturation of Intensity

The logistic transformation is defined as:

$$IEO_{sat} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-k(IEO_{linear} - x_0)}}$$

where:

- k controls the slope
- x_0 defines the inflection point

Initial values:

- $k = 1, x_0 = 1$

The function introduces saturation and regions of abrupt transition in the relation between environmental load and response probability.

2.5 Adjustment by Temporal Density

A densidade é incorporada como termo aditivo:

$$IEO_{inst}(t) = IEO_{sat}(t) + \delta z_D(t)$$

Density is incorporated as an additive term:

with $\delta = 0.10$ and the restriction $\delta \leq 0.20$.

The value is truncated to the interval $[0, 1]$.

Additionally, z_D is subjected to symmetric truncation before its incorporation into the index: $z_D = \text{clamp}[(D - \mu_D) / \sigma_D, -3, +3]$. This clamp prevents sessions of atypical duration, for example a session of a few seconds with multiple events, from producing extreme density values that would dominate the final adjustment. Truncation at three standard deviations preserves the relevant functional variability while discarding operational outliers.

2.6 Temporal Dynamics: Memory with Exponential Decay

The OEI incorporates historical dependence through a memory term with exponential decay:

$$IEO_{hist}(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t IEO_{inst}(\tau) e^{-\lambda(t-\tau)} d\tau$$

where λ represents the memory decay rate (equivalent to the functional recovery rate): high values of λ imply rapid decay of the contribution of past events, corresponding to accelerated functional recovery.

where λ denotes the memory decay rate (equivalent to the functional recovery rate): high values of λ imply rapid decay of the contribution of past events, corresponding to accelerated functional recovery.

The term defines a system with finite memory, in which the contribution of past events decays exponentially as a function of temporal distance.

2.7 Operational Discrete Form

For computational implementation, the recursive form is used:

$$\mathbf{IEO}_{\text{hist}}(\mathbf{t}) = \lambda \cdot \mathbf{IEO}_{\text{inst}}(\mathbf{t}) + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \mathbf{IEO}_{\text{hist}}(\mathbf{t} - 1)$$

allowing incremental updating of the time series.

The discrete form implements an exponential moving average (EMA) with smoothing factor λ . The coefficient λ weights the current instantaneous value and $(1-\lambda)$ weights the accumulated history. For small λ (typically $\lambda \in (0, 0.5]$), the coefficient $(1-\lambda)$ is numerically close to $e^{-\lambda}$, hence the correspondence with continuous decay. Under this convention: high values of λ increase the weight of the present instant and reduce historical memory (accelerated functional recovery); values close to zero preserve the cumulative contribution of past exposure for longer periods. When $\lambda \rightarrow 0$, the index converges to the equally weighted average of the entire history. The system does not diverge, since λ and $(1-\lambda)$ sum to 1. The EMA convention is adopted, with smoothing factor λ .

2.8 Final Form of the Index

$$\mathbf{IEO}(\mathbf{t}) = \mathbf{IEO}_{\text{hist}}(\mathbf{t})$$

The index integrates duration, frequency, intensity, density, and temporal dependence into a single continuous variable.

2.9 Epistemic Status of the Parameters

The model parameters are theoretically informed and provisional, defined to allow the initial operationalization of the variable. Calibration will be conducted by longitudinal analysis, based on the model's capacity to organize observable behavioral patterns.

Making these parameters explicit is part of the methodological procedure. The values $\alpha = 0.5$; $\beta = 0.3$; $\gamma = 0.2$; $\delta = 0.10$; $\lambda = 0.1$; $k = 1$; $x_0 = 1$ and $w_2/w_1 = 5.0$ are valid solely as initial values for the pilot study under way. Their extrapolation to the general population of digital forensic examiners, to other institutions, or for institutional decision-making purposes before the empirical calibration of Phase 2 constitutes a methodological error. No Red Flag generated

with the initial parameters should be interpreted as a clinical diagnosis or as grounds for a functional decision concerning the public servant.

2.10 Limitations and Open Parameters

The current formulation of the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI) incorporates weighting coefficients assigned to its core components (severity, duration, and rate of contact). These parameters (w_T , w_E , w_V) are treated as provisional values defined for the initial instantiation of the model. Their specification at this stage follows theoretical assumptions derived from Behavior Analysis, particularly the greater functional relevance of exposure duration relative to frequency and volumetric proxies.

The definitive calibration of these parameters is an empirical problem and represents a central objective of the subsequent validation stages of the system. Accordingly, the parameters should be interpreted as open variables, dependent on longitudinal data and subject to optimization. This treatment avoids the premature reification of the parameters and keeps the model an adaptive measurement system.

3. Architecture of SUPREME V4 as a System of Multimodal Measurement and Integration

SUPREME V4 is conceived as a system of continuous behavioral measurement, designed to quantify functional properties of the environment and their relation to changes in the operant repertoire, and not to evaluate individual performance. The system uses behavior as a channel of observation: it records events in the interaction with the digital environment, treated as permanent products of behavior organized into temporal sequences.

From these sequences, properties such as latency, duration, and density of responses are extracted, interpreted as traces of the functional relation between the organism and the environmental contingencies mediated by the platform, enabling the quantitative modeling of occupational exposure.

3.1 Measurement Principle: Logs as Behavioral Product

The system rests on the premise that operational records (logs) constitute permanent products of behavior under specific contingencies, analogous to the classical measures of rate and latency in experimental contexts.

Each recorded event (e.g., file opening, image viewing, video playback, evidence classification) is treated as an observable instance of organism-environment interaction. The temporal structure of these events makes it possible to derive fundamental behavioral properties, including inter-response latency, emission rate, and patterns of interruption and resumption.

3.1.1 Functional Validity of the Telemetry

The use of operational logs as the empirical base of the system does not imply a direct isomorphism between digital records and operant response classes. The recorded events constitute permanent products of behavior, but their functional interpretation requires caution regarding the presence of competing variables.

Inter-event latency, for example, may reflect either avoidance responses under aversive control or technical demands of the task, such as the analytic complexity of the material, hardware limitations, or external interruptions. Analogously, reductions in response rate may stem from cognitive demands specific to the case, and not necessarily from a motivational change.

SUPREME V4 treats telemetry metrics as probabilistic indicators of functional patterns, and not as direct equivalents of operant classes. The inference of escape and avoidance responses is made only when there is convergence among multiple behavioral indicators and a systematic relation between them and the variation in environmental load.

To mitigate confounding effects, the model incorporates complementary analytic strategies: (a) longitudinal intraindividual analysis, in which each organism functions as its own control; (b) modeling of contextual variables, such as operational interruptions and

administrative demands; and (c) assessment of the temporal consistency between changes in the OEI and subsequent changes in telemetry.

This approach preserves the functional sensitivity of the measures without assuming a direct equivalence between record and behavioral process, aligning the system with the validity criteria required for inference in naturalistic contexts.

3.2 Data Acquisition and Processing Architecture

SUPREME V4 operates on data generated by digital forensic tools (e.g., Griffeye, Cellebrite, IPED), using a passive ingestion model based on reading operational logs. The system incorporates an Agnostic Ingestion Core, designed to operate independently of specific platforms. Any system capable of generating records containing, at a minimum, a timestamp and an event category can be integrated into the analytic pipeline.

Collection and processing follow three structural principles:

- Non-intrusiveness, the absence of interference in the examiner's activity;
- Read-only mode, the preservation of the integrity of the forensic data;
- Pseudonymization, the separation between civil identity and behavioral series.

The processing pipeline converts raw events into behavioral metrics through the following sequential stages: (1) ingestion and standardization of events; (2) structural validation; (3) grouping into behavioral sessions; (4) extraction of behavioral metrics (T, E, V, D); (5) computation of the OEI; and (6) organization into time series for longitudinal analysis. The computation of the OEI incorporates a dynamic component dependent on the recent history, operationalized by a recursive term with exponential decay (see Sections 2.6 to 2.7).

A behavioral session is formally constructed from an ordered sequence of events such that: if $\Delta t_i \leq \tau$, the event belongs to the same session; if $\Delta t_i > \tau$, a new session begins. The value $\tau = 300$ seconds (5 minutes) is adopted as the inactivity threshold. Operational constraints include a minimum duration of 5 seconds and a maximum of 12 hours per session.

3.3 Multimodal Integration Architecture

SUPREME V4 integrates multiple sources of behavioral data, organized into three complementary analytic axes:

Axis I, Exposure Intensity (OEI): represents the independent variable of the model, operationalizing the magnitude of the aversive environmental load in each time window.

Axis II, Operant Telemetry (Logs): constitutes the primary dependent variable, derived directly from the operational records. The main metrics include inter-response latency, event rate, and fragmentation of the behavioral pattern. Under aversive contingencies, increases in latency and interruptions are consistent with the emergence of escape and avoidance responses, as described by Sidman (1989).

Axis III, Verbal Behavior (Psychometrics): consists of self-reported measures of affective state (e.g., PANAS-short), collected at high frequency or triggered by specific exposure conditions. These measures are treated as verbal behavior under the control of social and institutional contingencies, not as direct access to internal states.

3.4 Integration Principle: Functional Congruence

The system operates under the principle of functional congruence among axes: the interpretation of the system's state results from the relation among environmental load (OEI), operant response (telemetry), and verbal behavior (psychometrics), and not from a single data source. Divergence among these axes is treated as relevant analytic information.

3.5 Risk-State Detection Algorithm (Red Flags)

SUPREME V4 implements a system for detecting pre-symptomatic patterns based on the dynamics among the three axes. These patterns are formalized as categories of functional alert:

3.5.1 Reactivity Red Flag (Concordance)

Defined by the co-occurrence of a significant increase in the OEI ($OEI_linear \geq 1.5$) and an immediate change in affective measures (a reduction in positive affect or an increase in negative affect). This pattern indicates a system in which there is correspondence between environmental load and verbal response, suggesting preserved functional sensitivity to the contingencies.

3.5.2 Dissonance Red Flag (Masked Risk)

Characterized by the combination of three simultaneous criteria (AND logic): (a) $OEI_linear \geq 2.0$ (equivalent to $OEI_sat \approx 0.73$ under $k = 1$ and $x_0 = 1$); (b) objective behavioral changes measured by an increase in inter-response latency greater than 1.5 SD from the individual baseline, or fragmentation of the engagement pattern above 1.5 SD; and (c) psychometric variation below 1.0 SD from baseline (absence of a signal in self-report). All three criteria must be satisfied simultaneously for the alert to activate. This dissociation is interpreted as a possible effect of social contingencies that maintain stability in self-report, while functional changes are already occurring in performance.

Clinical Relevance of the Dissonance Red Flag In occupational contexts marked by an institutional culture of invulnerability, such as intelligence and criminal forensic units, the suppression of self-reported suffering is expected and documented in the literature (Mitchell et al., 2023; Gewirtz-Meydan et al., 2024). The Dissonance Red Flag is the pattern of greatest clinical and preventive relevance in the system, precisely because it detects risk where an assessment based exclusively on self-report would produce a false negative.

3.5.3 Chronicity Red Flag

Identified when the OEI returns to normative levels (OEI_linear below 1.0), but behavioral or psychometric indicators remain deteriorated at a level above 1.0 SD from baseline for three or more consecutive biweekly windows. This pattern suggests an accumulation of exposure effects, with reduced functional recovery between work periods. The threshold of three windows (six weeks) is provisional and will be empirically calibrated in the pilot study.

3.6 Separation between Analytic Layers

The system architecture distinguishes three levels: (1) raw events, operational records; (2) behavioral metrics, derived variables; and (3) analytic states (Red Flags), functional inferences. This separation ensures full traceability and avoids confusion between observed datum and analytic interpretation.

3.7 Function of the System in the Theoretical Model

Within the scope of the present work, SUPREME V4 acts as an instrument for measuring the independent variable (OEI) and as a system for detecting functional patterns in behavior. Its function is to enable continuous observation of the relation among environmental exposure intensity, changes in the operant repertoire, and the dynamics of verbal behavior. This articulation makes possible the transition from models based on internal states to a functional model, based on relations between environmental variables and observable behavior.

4. Limitations and Open Parameters

This section organizes the limitations of the model into three levels: (i) limitations inherent to the theoretical model; (ii) empirical parameters pending calibration; and (iii) contextual and generalization limitations. Making these limitations explicit is part of the methodological procedure of the proposal.

4.1 Limitations of the Theoretical Model

The OEI is proposed as a structured environmental proxy of occupational aversive load, operationalized from observable properties of the stimulus, and not as a measure of the subjective aversive value of the material. The institutional severity classification (based on adapted COPINE criteria) does not capture idiosyncratic responses: content that acquires particular meaning for a given examiner, as a function of life history, a previously installed avoidance repertoire, or specific features of the case, may exert aversive control disproportionate to the weight assigned by the system.

This limitation is partially mitigated by the intraindividual structure of the model: standardization by the individual baseline preserves the functional variability of each organism and reduces the impact of comparisons between individuals with distinct exposure histories.

Additionally, the model does not exhaustively control for the cumulative history of exposure over the years prior to the study, which may produce effects of differential habituation or sensitization among participants. Future studies should incorporate measures of pre-study cumulative exposure as a covariate.

It is also acknowledged that behavioral telemetry metrics are context-dependent inferential indicators, subject to the influence of competing variables such as technical demands of the task, system characteristics, and organizational contingencies.

The model mitigates this limitation through intraindividual analysis and triangulation among multiple axes, preserving the need for continuous functional validation. Future studies should investigate the sensitivity and specificity of these indicators in distinguishing avoidance patterns from variations arising from operational demands.

4.2 Parameters Pending Empirical Calibration

The following parameters await empirical calibration in the pilot study under way:

- Linear combination weights ($\alpha = 0.5$, $\beta = 0.3$, $\gamma = 0.2$): reflect the functional hierarchy among duration, frequency, and exposure volume. The restriction $\alpha > \beta > \gamma$ and $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$ is maintained as an invariant; the specific values will be adjusted by sensitivity analysis.
- Logistic function parameters ($k = 1$; $x_0 = 1$): control the slope and the inflection point of the saturation curve. Initial values were defined to produce mathematically well-behaved behavior in the expected range of variation of OEI_linear.
-
- Density coefficient ($\delta = 0.10$): captures the adjustment for temporal pressure. The maximum limit of $\delta \leq 0.20$ is maintained as an invariant to ensure that density does not dominate the final index.
- Memory decay rate ($\lambda \in (0, 0.5]$): controls the relative weight between the current instantaneous value and the accumulated history in the time series. In the discrete

form, $OEI_hist(t) = \lambda \cdot OEI_inst(t) + (1-\lambda) \cdot OEI_hist(t-1)$, λ weights the present instant and $(1-\lambda)$ weights the memory. High values of λ imply greater weight on the current instant and less historical memory (accelerated functional recovery); values close to zero preserve the cumulative memory for long periods. The index converges in both cases, since $\lambda + (1-\lambda) = 1$. Initial value: $\lambda = 0.1$ (to be empirically calibrated).

- Severity ratio ($w_2/w_1 = 5.0$): expresses the qualitative discontinuity between the Alpha class (COPINE 1–3) and the Beta class (COPINE 4–10). This is a functional rupture, not a linear gradation, and will be empirically assessed by analysis of the ratio $\rho = \beta_3/\beta_2$ in the linear mixed models.
- Session threshold $\tau = 300$ seconds: defines the inactivity criterion for grouping events into behavioral sessions. A conservative value adopted to capture relevant behavioral interruptions without excessive fragmentation of the interaction flow.

4.3 Generalization and Context Limitations

The pilot study under way is conducted in a specific Brazilian federal institutional context, with a small convenience sample. The analytic focus privileges internal validity and intraindividual modeling of trajectories, in which each participant acts as its own control. The central inference falls on functional relations observed at the level of the individual, not on broad population estimates.

Voluntary-adherence bias may operate in distinct directions: examiners in greater distress may decline participation for fear of institutional exposure, while others may join motivated by the possibility of monitoring and care. In both cases, the composition of the sample may distort the real distribution of psychological reactivity in the unit.

The functional analysis may be influenced by organizational variables that are not fully controllable: administrative interruptions, meetings, and bureaucratic tasks carried out in parallel with the use of the forensic software may generate patterns of apparent inactivity that do not correspond to functional avoidance. This confounding will be mitigated by an

institutional diary, a contextual checklist, and modeling with dummy variables in the sensitivity analyses.

Finally, the risk of reactivity to monitoring (Hawthorne effect) is acknowledged. The initial calibration phase has precisely the function of reducing the novelty effect and capturing more stable behavioral patterns before the full application of the analytic criteria.

5. Empirical Calibration and Feasibility Plan

Data collection for the naturalistic study is planned to begin in October 2026, in a sentinel unit of the Federal Police of Brazil, following approval by the Research Ethics Committee. The protocol is structured in two sequential phases. The first is a pilot study with $N = 6$ digital forensic examiners (3 with regular exposure to CSAM and 3 controls), with monitoring over approximately 8 weeks (the individual baseline closing at week 3), planned for October to December 2026; this phase is intended for the operational validation of the collection protocol, the empirical estimation of the ratio $\rho = \beta_3/\beta_2$, and the generation of a provisional OEI equation. The second is the main doctoral study, with approximately 30 examiners, planned for February to May 2027, intended for the intraindividual modeling of trajectories and the refinement of the parameters of the complete pipeline. Both phases include structured records of exposure windows (AEJE) and, when available, logs from forensic tools and the application of a high-frequency psychometric battery (PANAS-short, DASS-21, OLBI, SRQ-20).

The present article is a theoretical and methodological formalization, deposited prior to the start of data collection; it therefore reports no empirical results. The empirical calibration of the parameters will be reported in subsequent publications, after the pilot study (planned for completion in December 2026) and the main study (planned for 2027).

Methodological Note on the Pilot Study as a Feasibility Study The sample size of $N = 6$ (3 exposed and 3 controls) is dimensioned for operational feasibility and the generation of

preliminary parameter estimates, not for hypothesis confirmation. The intraindividual longitudinal design confers analytic power through the density of repeated measures over time, and not through cross-sectional sample size. Each participant functions as its own control. This framing is methodologically consistent with the declared feasibility objectives.

6. Discussion

The present work proposes a reframing of the problem of occupational health in high aversive-exposure contexts, with a focus on CSAM forensics. The central shift, which moves from internalist constructs to functional relations between environment and behavior, is not merely a change of language. It is a redefinition of the unit of analysis, the method of measurement, and the strategies of intervention.

6.1 Positioning Relative to the Existing Literature

The literature on the psychological impact of CSAM exposure extensively documents outcomes such as post-traumatic stress, anxiety, depression, occupational exhaustion, and, more recently, post-traumatic stress of a sexual nature, a phenomenon in which the trauma becomes incorporated into the professional's intimate behavioral patterns (Gewirtz-Meydan et al., 2023). Studies with samples of 470 to 500 North American professionals found that the severity of the content, far more than the volume or frequency of exposure, was the only parameter independently associated with elevated post-traumatic stress symptoms (Mitchell et al., 2023).

The contribution of the present model relative to this literature is twofold. First, rather than treating exposure as a binary variable (exposed/not exposed) or a coarse ordinal one, the OEI operationalizes it as a continuous, composite variable with high temporal resolution. Second, rather than relying exclusively on periodic self-report, the system integrates behavioral telemetry as the primary dependent variable, capturing functional changes before they crystallize into declared clinical symptoms.

This positioning is consistent with the methodological critique of Gullon-Scott and Johnson (2024), who identified among British investigators a prevalence of 30% of secondary traumatic stress at severe levels, suggesting systematic underdetection in contexts with a strong culture of institutional invulnerability. The Dissonance Red Flag of SUPREME V4 is designed precisely to operate where self-report produces a false negative.

6.2 The OEI as a Methodological Advance

There is, as far as the present review identified, no published model that operationalizes occupational exposure to CSAM as a continuous variable derived from behavioral telemetry in a naturalistic context. Prior initiatives, such as the Self-Assessment Tool of Mitchell et al. (2024), constitute important advances, but operate exclusively at the level of self-report and in a univariate format.

The OEI, by contrast, is multidimensional (it integrates T, E, V, and D), intraindividual (standardized by the organism's own baseline), continuous (computed biweekly through time series), and platform-agnostic (it operates on any system capable of generating logs with a timestamp and an event category).

These properties make the OEI compatible with measurement requirements that self-report systems structurally do not satisfy: pre-symptomatic capture, high temporal resolution, and independence from social contingencies that suppress the report of suffering.

6.3 Implications for Systems Engineering and Institutional Policies

SUPREME V4 shifts the focus of intervention from individual attributes to properties of the work environment. This has direct implications for institutional policies: rather than identifying “who is suffering” and triggering a reactive clinical response, the system makes it possible to identify “when the environment exceeds functional thresholds” and to trigger a preventive systemic response.

This distinction is particularly relevant in institutions such as the Federal Police, where the reputational cost of admitting psychological suffering can be high for the individual servant.

The passive, non-intrusive, and pseudonymized monitoring of SUPREME V4 reduces this cost, dissociating the health datum from the professional's functional identity.

6.4 Limitations of the Discussion and Future Directions

The claims in this section are theoretical propositions and functional hypotheses, not confirmed empirical assertions. The direct test of the hypothesis of behavioral precedence, that changes in workflow (telemetry) temporally precede psychometric elevations, is the central objective of the pilot study under way and of the subsequent longitudinal studies.

Priority directions for future research include: (1) empirical calibration of the OEI parameters with the pilot data; (2) testing the hypothesis of behavioral precedence through cross-lagged analysis; (3) convergent validation of the OEI with external measures of workload; (4) extension of the model to other populations exposed to systematic aversive content (e.g., digital platform moderators, intelligence analysts); and (5) development of an environmental intervention protocol based on the functional thresholds identified by the system.

7. Conclusion

The present work formalized the theoretical, mathematical, and architectural foundations of the Occupational Exposure Index (OEI) and the SUPREME V4 system. The central proposal, to treat aversive exposure load as a quantifiable establishing operation, derived from behavioral telemetry in a naturalistic context, represents a functional reframing of the field that shifts measurement from internal states to observable relations between environment and behavior.

The model should be understood as an initial operational formalization, whose validity depends on its capacity to predict and organize observable behavioral patterns. Its consolidation will not come from internal consistency in isolation, but from the progressive empirical calibration of its parameters and from the demonstration of analytic utility on real data.

The empirical calibration under way will provide specific estimates for the population of Brazilian digital forensic examiners, without altering the formal structure of the proposal.

The results of the pilot study will be integrated into a subsequent version, submitted to a peer-reviewed journal.

References

- Ferster, C. B., & Skinner, B. F. (1957). Schedules of reinforcement. Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Gewirtz-Meydan, A., Mitchell, K. J., & O'Brien, J. E. (2023). Sexual posttraumatic stress among investigators of child sexual abuse material. *Policing: A Journal of Policy and Practice*, 17, paad052. <https://doi.org/10.1093/police/paad052>
- Gewirtz-Meydan, A., Mitchell, K. J., & O'Brien, J. E. (2024). Trauma behind the keyboard: Exploring disparities in child sexual abuse materials exposure and mental health factors among investigators and forensic examiners — A network analysis. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 152, 106757. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2024.106757>
- Gilbert, T. F. (1978). *Human competence: Engineering worthy performance*. McGraw-Hill.
- Gullon-Scott, F., & Johnson, K. (2024). Secondary traumatic stress among digital forensic examiners in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Investigative Psychology and Offender Profiling*, 21(1), 14–29. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jip.1632>
- Hernandez, E., & Hernandez, A. (2024). Psychological impact of exposure to child sexual abuse material among forensic professionals: A systematic review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 25(2), 1234–1251. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15248380231155806>
- Lindsley, O. R. (1991). Precision teaching's unique legacy from B. F. Skinner. *Journal of Behavioral Education*, 1(2), 253–266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00957007>
- Michael, J. (1993). Establishing operations. *The Behavior Analyst*, 16(2), 191–206. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03392623>
- Mitchell, K. J., Gewirtz-Meydan, A., Finkelhor, D., O'Brien, J. E., & Jones, L. M. (2023). The mental health of officials who regularly examine child sexual abuse material: Strategies for harm mitigation. *BMC Psychiatry*, 23, 940. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-05370-y>
- Mitchell, K. J., Gewirtz-Meydan, A., & O'Brien, J. E. (2024). A self-assessment tool for helping identify police burnout among investigators of child sexual abuse material. *APSAC Advisor*, 36(1), 12–20.
- O'Brien, J. E., Gewirtz-Meydan, A., & Mitchell, K. J. (2024). Emotional wellbeing and cognitive appraisals among law enforcement exposed to child sexually explicit materials. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 51(3), 456–472. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00938548231210514>

- Rachlin, H. (1994). *Behavior and mind: The roots of modern psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Rachlin, H. (2000). *The science of self-control*. Harvard University Press.
- Sidman, M. (1989). *Coercion and its fallout*. Authors Cooperative.
- Skinner, B. F. (1938). *The behavior of organisms: An experimental analysis*. Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Skinner, B. F. (1953). *Science and human behavior*. Macmillan.
- Watson, D., Clark, L. A., & Tellegen, A. (1988). Development and validation of brief measures of positive and negative affect: The PANAS scales. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 54(6), 1063–1070. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.54.6.1063>
- Bar-Haim, Y., Lamy, D., Pergamin, L., Bakermans-Kranenburg, M. J., & van IJzendoorn, M. H. (2007). Threat-related attentional bias in anxious and nonanxious individuals: A meta-analytic study. *Psychological Bulletin*, 133(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.133.1.1>
- Kimhy, D., Vakhrusheva, J., Liu, Y., Wang, Y., Trost, Z., Choi, C. J., & Khan, S. (2020). Emotion awareness and regulation in schizophrenia: Implications for social functioning. *Psychiatry Research*, 286, 112884. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.112884>
- MacLeod, C., Rutherford, E., Campbell, L., Ebsworthy, G., & Holker, L. (2002). Selective attention and emotional vulnerability: Assessing the causal basis of their association through the experimental manipulation of attentional bias. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 111(1), 107–123. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-843X.111.1.107>
- Trull, T. J., & Ebner-Priemer, U. (2020). Ambulatory assessment in psychopathology research: A review of recommended reporting guidelines and current practices. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 129(1), 56–63. <https://doi.org/10.1037/abn0000473>